

Generation of Entangled Photon Pairs from a Silicon Bichromatic Photonic Crystal Cavity

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(Dated: 24 May 2024)

Integrated quantum photonics leverages the on-chip generation of nonclassical states of light to realize key functionalities of quantum devices. Typically, the generation of such nonclassical states relies on whispering gallery mode resonators, such as integrated optical micro-rings, which enhance the efficiency of the underlying spontaneous nonlinear processes. While this kind of resonators excel in maximizing either the temporal confinement or the spatial overlap between different resonant modes, they are usually associated with large mode volumes, imposing an intrinsic limitation on the device efficiency and footprint. Here, we engineer a source of time-energy entangled photon pairs based on a silicon photonic crystal cavity, implemented in a fully CMOS-compatible platform. In this device, resonantly enhanced spontaneous four-wave mixing converts pump photon pairs into signal/idler photon pairs at the energy-conserving condition in the telecommunication C-band. The design of the resonator is based on an effective bichromatic confinement potential, allowing to achieve up to 9 close-to-equally spaced modes in frequency, while preserving small mode volumes, and the whole chip, including grating couplers and access waveguides, is fabricated in a single run on a silicon-on-insulator platform. Besides demonstrating efficient photon pair generation, we also implement a Franson-type interference experiment, demonstrating entanglement between signal and idler photons with a Bell inequality violation exceeding 5 standard deviations. The high generation efficiency combined with the small device footprint in a CMOS-compatible integrated structure opens a pathway towards the implementation of compact quantum light sources in all-silicon photonic platforms.

I. INTRODUCTION

Integrated photonics has emerged as the platform of choice for several quantum technologies. The ability to fabricate many different devices on the same chip, using the same well-established technology developed for microelectronic circuits¹, allows for functionalities that are otherwise unattainable, despite being fundamental for the implementation of many quantum information protocols². The generation of nonclassical states of light through suitably engineered photonic devices plays a pivotal role for quantum photonic applications. In particular, these are the devices where typically entanglement, a genuine quantum property, is created. In integrated photonics, sources of entangled photon pairs typically rely on spontaneous nonlinear light-matter interaction, which is enhanced by resonant structures³⁻⁸. In particular, spontaneous four wave mixing (SFWM) is the process of choice for silicon and silicon-based devices, in which an intrinsic third-order nonlinear susceptibility exists.

Several different types of resonant structures can be employed to efficiently enhance SFWM⁹. Among these, whispering gallery mode resonators, such as rings, microtoroids or microspheres¹⁰⁻¹², naturally fulfill the energy conservation and phase-matching requirements, at least in the wavelength ranges in which waveguide dispersion can be neglected. However, these choices typically entail large modal volumes, while the generation efficiency scales as a power

of the ratio between the resonance quality factor and the effective confinement volume, Q/V .³ The same is not true for standing-wave resonators; photonic Crystals (PhC), and particularly photonic crystal cavities, can serve as a tool to confine light in a diffraction-limited mode volume while keeping large Q-factors,^{13,14} thus exhibiting nearly optimal Q/V ratios at a given wavelength. On the other hand, in fully confined geometries the phase-matching condition is replaced by the mode overlap for standing waves, and energy conservation is not trivially met¹⁵⁻¹⁷. In this work, we experimentally show how silicon photonic crystal cavities fabricated in a fully CMOS-compatible platform can be engineered to obtain a high-brightness integrated source of pure time-energy entangled photon pairs. By exploiting evenly spaced high-Q resonances obtained in the quasi-harmonic potential of a silicon bichromatic photonic crystal cavity^{18,19}, we hereby engineer the whole integrated chip, including input/output sub-wavelength grating couplers, access waveguides, and photonic crystal input/output waveguides coupled to the targeted bichromatic cavity, which allows to efficiently excite the pump resonance and extract the generated signal and idler frequencies. Despite the intrinsic presence of two-photon absorption in silicon, which might have hindered the actual detection of quantum effects in devices with such small confinement volumes, we experimentally demonstrate the emission of photon pairs with an estimated generation efficiency as high as ~ 11.7 MHz/mW² and a measured on-chip emission rate up

to 120 kHz. In addition, in order to showcase the suitability of our device for applications in photonic quantum technologies, we perform an experiment showing that the spontaneously generated photon pairs are indeed time-energy entangled, by assessing a Bell's inequality violation by more than 5 standard deviations in a Franson interferometry configuration²⁰. The latter represents the first experimental demonstration of time-energy entangled photons from a single photonic crystal cavity in a pure silicon membrane.

II. SAMPLE DESIGN AND FABRICATION

The device developed in this work consists of a single, multi-mode photonic crystal cavity with a bichromatic design. Such cavity geometry was originally proposed in Ref.¹⁸, and later demonstrated in several material platforms^{19,21–23}. This type of resonator was soon recognized to display an harmonic-like effective confinement potential, that results in a spectrum of high-quality factor modes²², which was then exploited to demonstrate the first optical parametric oscillator based on a photonic crystal resonator²³. In our implementation of such ‘‘bichromatic cavity’’, we start from a line-defect in a triangular lattice of circular air holes with a lattice constant a , in which an entire row of holes with reduced radius is shifted by half a period, and its lattice constant a' is slightly mismatched with respect to the one of the surrounding lattice. In fact, we impose their ratio to follow the relation $a'/a = N/(N+1)$, where N represents the number of periods a' inserted in the cavity region before matching the lattice of the surrounding photonic crystal, a . The aperiodic distribution of the dielectric constant in the cavity region acts as an effective parabolic potential for photons (Fig. 1a), such that the energy levels (*viz.* the localized cavity modes) in the photonic band gap are arranged in a way that mimics the behavior of a quantum harmonic oscillator. Hence, nearly equally spaced resonances are obtained, with small deviations due to the non-perfect parabolicity of the effective potential²².

In the perspective of device integration, here we presented a sample to be measured with in-plane transmission/reflection spectroscopy, exploiting input/output access waveguides that are evanescently coupled to the central resonator, as shown in Fig. 1b. The entire chip layout was thus designed to allow for input/output fiber coupling through sub-wavelength grating couplers²⁴, yielding simpler experimental coupling schemes compared to previous works on similar platforms^{7,25}. Such single-etch grating couplers convey light to standard ridge silicon-on-insulator (SOI) waveguides, which become suspended before transitioning to W1.05 or W1.3 photonic crystal waveguides (*i.e.*, standard line-defect in a triangular lattice whose width is increased by a factor 1.05 or 1.3, respectively); we estimated approximately 8dB of insertion losses per grating coupler; the larger insertion losses here reported as compared to Ref.²⁴ may be attributed to propagation losses due to stitching defects in the coupling ridge waveguide. As it is evident from Fig. 1b, the input/output coupling is symmetric with respect to the cavity center, and the evanescent coupling is engineered through numerical simulations by 3D-FDTD as

a function of the horizontal and vertical distance of the waveguide ends from this center, parametrized by n_x and n_y periods of distance from it.

The spectral characterization of the devices yields typically a comb-like multimode structure in either reflection or transmission.^{19,22} In particular, we are able to assess up to 9 resonances in a single device. A statistics of the relative detuning among the first three triplets is summarized in Fig. 2. Here, $\delta\Delta_{ijk} = \nu_k + \nu_i - 2\nu_j$ is the detuning from the triply-resonant (*i.e.* equal frequency spacing) condition for triplets of adjacent resonances. The average detuning is within 25 GHz for the three triplets examined, with a standard deviation of 60 GHz, on average. Despite the bichromatic cavity approximating a harmonic oscillator, it is challenging, from a technological point of view, to achieve perfect energy matching in the fabricated device, especially when dealing with high-Q resonances. Out of the adjacent triplets of 54 cavities, 13 triplets have an FSR lower than 10GHz, and only three of those lower than 5GHz. From this systematic characterization, we selected a device with nearly equally spaced resonances, shown in Fig. 1c, corresponding to a bichromatic PhC cavity with parameters $N = 48$, $a = 400\text{nm}$ $n_x = 4$ and $n_y = 5$, respectively. A Lorentzian fit of the spectral lineshape of each resonance transmission gives Q-factors for signal, pump and idler as high as $Q_i \simeq 50,000$, $Q_p \simeq 90,000$ and $Q_i \simeq 65,000$, respectively. Whereas, from the dip visibility in the reflection spectra, the coupling efficiency can be estimated to be $\eta_s = 0.62$, $\eta_p = 0.42$ and $\eta_i = 0.93$ for the signal, pump and idler modes, respectively. The reflection signal is modulated by Fabry-Pérot (FP) interference fringes most probably originated from reflections between the output grating coupler and the high impedance interface between the ridge waveguide and the PhC waveguide. In order to estimate the visibility of the reflection dips, we have fitted the spectra with a heuristic model, *i.e.*, a combination of a sinusoidal function for the FP fringes and a Fano lineshape for the cavity mode resonance, from which the visibility is extracted. By tuning the laser on-resonance, we estimated an overall chip insertion loss $\alpha_s = 11.6\text{dB}$, $\alpha_p = 11.5\text{dB}$ and $\alpha_i = 8.5\text{dB}$, respectively, between the input and output fiber. The bichromatic design ensures that the resonances are nearly evenly spaced, on average. For the case of the device measured in this work to probe entangled photon pair generation, we quantify the detuning $\delta\Delta_{spi} = 9.5\text{GHz}$, which is actually larger than the average linewidth of the resonances $\overline{\delta\nu} = 3.5\text{GHz}$. This detuning certainly plays a detrimental role, lowering the overall efficiency. In fact, the overall efficiency is proportional to the symmetric overlap integral of the resonances with respect to the pump frequency,^{23,26} *i.e.*, $\rho_{int} \propto \int \mathcal{L}_p^2(\omega_p) \mathcal{L}_s(\omega_p + \Omega) \mathcal{L}_i(\omega_p - \Omega) d\Omega$, which, for the triplet hereby considered, is approximately two orders of magnitude smaller than the perfectly matched configuration²⁷. Nevertheless, as shown in the next section, this is enough to show the spontaneous generation of signal/idler pairs and it does not hinder the observation of time-bin entanglement with relatively high efficiency, thus leaving a large room for improvement by exploiting post-fabrication tuning processes to achieve an even better energy matching.¹⁹

III. RESULTS

Here we report the quantum photonic performances obtained from the device whose transmission spectrum is shown in Fig. 1c. As already mentioned, the selected cavity exhibits a good trade-off between relatively low insertion losses and a detuning of 9.5 GHz for the first triplet.

Figure 3 shows a complete scheme of the experimental setup. In order to measure time correlations, the interferometer section is bypassed. The input laser (EXFO T100S-HP) is used to pump the spontaneous process. A narrowband tunable passband filter (Santec OTF-350) is used to filter out the laser amplified spontaneous emission. Two fiber arrays polished at the angle required by the grating design (18°) are used for in and out coupling. At the output of the sample, the pump is suppressed via a Bragg filter tuned to the pump wavelength rejecting 35 dB, then the entangled pair is separated and spectrally filtered with free-space tunable bandpass filters (Semrock). The signal and idler photons are then routed to two independent superconducting nanowire single photon detectors (SNSPDs) to measure temporal correlations between the arrival times (Fig. 4a). By studying the dependence of the integrated coincidence peak as a function of the pump power, we retrieved the expected quadratic dependence, as shown in Fig. 4b. We do not observe any complex behavior of the generation trend due, e.g., to the thermo-optic contribution acting as a differential tuning of the resonances of the targeted triplet, as observed, e.g., in other material platforms.^{23,28} Multiple factors may play a role in this respect. Because of the higher thermal conductivity of silicon, the inhomogeneity of the spatial thermal profile is less severe than, e.g., in Ref.²³, so all the resonances shift rigidly and the triplet tuning is less affected. Moreover, because of the non-negligible detuning of this particular triplet, the main energy matching contribution comes from the tails of the Lorentzian lineshapes, hence we are less sensitive to an eventual detuning.

In order to assess the time-energy entangled nature of the generated photon pairs, we performed a Franson interferometry experiment^{10,20,29}. In our case, being a loophole-free experiment beyond the scope of this work, we used a single fiber-based Mach-Zehnder interferometer as a folded Franson interferometer³⁰, as shown in Fig. 3. To prevent first-order interference between the generated photons, the unbalance between the two arms $\Delta L = 2$ m is required to be larger than the coherence length of each photon in the pair $L_{s,i} \approx 13.5$ cm, but shorter than the coherence length of the wavefunction, i.e., the coherence length of the pump laser $L_p^{ext} \approx 1$ km. To avoid phase drifts associated with local temperature fluctuations, the interferometer is stabilized on a reference stable laser (Orbits Lightwave Eternal) whereas the phase difference between the arms can be finely controlled with a fiber phase shifter with an accuracy below 3 mrad. The biphoton state at the output of the interferometer can be written in the time-bin encoding picture, labelling as S and L the short and long path, respectively. Intuitively, the two photons can undergo four possible path combinations, that result in a superposition state at the output of the interferometer among all the possible combinations $|LL\rangle$, $|SS\rangle$, $|SL\rangle$ and $|LS\rangle$. However, the two combina-

tions $|LL\rangle$ and $|SS\rangle$ are indistinguishable and therefore exhibit a Franson-type quantum interference. By post-selecting on such combinations, the output state can be represented by the wavefunction:

$$|\psi\rangle = \frac{|SS\rangle + e^{i(\phi_s + \phi_i)} |LL\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} \quad (1)$$

being ϕ_s and ϕ_i the phases accumulated by the signal and idler photons, respectively. Given the aforementioned indistinguishability between the $|LL\rangle$ and $|SS\rangle$ combinations, and the phase dependence given by the sum of idler and signal photon phase $2\phi = \phi_i + \phi_s$, the measured coincidence rate associated with the state $|\psi\rangle$ is expected to follow the trend¹⁰:

$$C(\phi) = C_0 (1 + \cos(2\phi)) \quad (2)$$

being $2C_0$ the peak coincidence rate and ϕ a phase offset. Fig. 4c shows the stack of histograms retrieved from the collected coincidences. The cavity has been driven with -9 dBm of coupled power. The central peak, associated with post-selection on the state $|\psi\rangle$, shows a clear sinusoidal interference pattern, as shown in Fig. 4d. In order to prove a violation of Bell's inequality, the visibility of the fringes should be greater than $1/\sqrt{2}$. From a fit of the fringes, we retrieved a visibility of $85.5 \pm 2.5\%$ corresponding to a violation of Bell's inequality exceeding 5 standard deviations, which confirms the time-energy entangled nature of the generated state.

IV. DISCUSSION

We have presented a novel integrated source of time-energy entangled photon pairs, based on a photonic crystal resonator realized in a silicon photonic platform. The bichromatic cavity design proved to be a powerful approach for the realization of nearly-equally spaced resonances, capable to support triply resonant spontaneous four-wave mixing processes, while at the same time ensuring a minimal mode volume, as small as $1.6(\lambda/n)^3$ for the fundamental mode³¹. In terms of generation efficiency of the spontaneously emitted signal/idler photon pairs, after accounting for insertion losses $\eta_{s,p,i}$ and detection efficiency $\epsilon_{QE} = 0.85$, from the fit of the scaling trend in Fig. 4b, we can estimate a normalized internal pair generation efficiency as high as

$$\rho_{\text{int}} = \frac{1}{\eta_p^2 \eta_s \eta_i} \frac{R_{\text{ext}}}{P_{\text{ext}}^2 \epsilon_{QE}^2} \simeq 11.7 \frac{\text{MHz}}{\text{mW}^2}, \quad (3)$$

and a maximum internal pair generation rate as high as 132 kHz for a coupled input power as small as 120 μ W.

Compared to integrated photon pair sources based on travelling wave resonators³²⁻³⁴, our device displays a footprint of only 230 μm^2 , which benefits from by the extreme confinement capability from the PhC localization mechanism. Furthermore, the use of a multimode cavity results in a more compact and easier to design resonators than the PhC cavity solutions demonstrated so far^{7,35-37}, which relied on coupled resonators or dispersion-engineered PhC waveguides, both in

terms of device footprint and mode volume. In terms of performance, our device displays a normalized generation efficiency comparable to previous results obtained in silicon PhC cavities⁷. Despite the larger frequency detuning in the present case, our device exhibits a 20-fold improvement in generation efficiency compared to previous results based on microring resonators with similar quality factors³⁴.

Despite these advantages, our source suffers from several extrinsic limitations that currently hinder the full potential of our approach. In particular, the statistic deviation from the triply-resonant condition still obliges to compromise between quality factor (and therefore field-enhancement) and generation efficiency, as the employment of narrower resonances reflects in tighter spectral alignment conditions. Specifically, the device presented here suffers from a deviation of 9.5 GHz (about 2.7 linewidths), which we estimate to reduce the maximal generation efficiency by approximately one order of magnitude²³. This issue could be mitigated on one hand by further improving the fabrication, whereas advanced techniques have allowed to demonstrate PhC cavities with Q factors exceeding 10^7 .¹⁴ On the other hand, the detuning issue could be addressed by implementing post-fabrication fine-tuning techniques, for example by laser-assisted local oxidation of the silicon membrane¹⁹, which were proven capable to fully recover the triply resonant condition for small values of initial detuning. Finally, while the purpose of this work included proving the compatibility with the silicon photonics platform, we remark that the presence of two-photon absorption ultimately poses a limitation to the maximum pump power in our device. In this perspective, silicon nitride, silicon oxynitride and silicon carbide materials represent good CMOS-compatible alternatives, albeit the lower performance when compared to silicon devices. Another further alternative is offered by III/V materials, which have proven to reach pair generation rates in the >10 MHz range³⁸, being only limited in pump power by higher-order emission, ultimately resulting in the emergence of parametric oscillations²³. In summary, we have shown here a micrometer-scale footprint, highly-efficient source of entangled photon pairs realized in integrated silicon photonics technology. By leveraging the mature CMOS-compatible fabrication, this demonstration opens a pathway towards the engineering of highly-compact and power-efficient quantum devices, a crucial aspect in the perspective large-scale integration of multi-component, complex quantum devices^{34,39-41}.

V. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work was supported by the EU H2020 QuantERA ERA-NET Co-fund in Quantum Technologies project CUSPIDOR, co-funded by the Italian Ministry of Education, University and Research (MIUR) as well as by the Austrian Science Foundation FWF under Project I 3760-N27. Additionally, the work received support from the Italian Ministry of Research (MUR) through the grant ‘Dipartimenti di Eccellenza’ 2018-2022 (F11I18000680001), and PNRR MUR project ‘National Quantum Science and Technology Institute’

– NQSTI (PE0000023). A.B. and D.B. acknowledge funding from the HyperSpace project (project ID 101070168), co-funded from the EU and the Natural Sciences and Engineering Research Council of Canada (NSERC). The authors acknowledge Alma Halilovic and Stephan Bräuer for cleanroom and other technical supports. A. De Rossi and A. Chopin and gratefully acknowledged for useful scientific discussions.

VI. DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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FIG. 1: (a) Schematic visualization of the localization mechanism for the bichromatic photonic crystal cavity, displaying a quasi-harmonic trapping potential at low energy, which yields resonant modes (filled plots) that are, ideally, evenly spaced in energy. Moreover, such harmonic modes naturally display a Gauss-Hermite envelope (solid lines). (b) Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) image of one of the fabricated devices. The cavity region is highlighted in blue, while the access waveguides (W1.3 in this figure) are marked in yellow. We may assume identical in- and out-coupling between the access waveguides and the central cavity, represented by the coefficient Γ_c , while Γ_{rad} represents out-of-plane scattering losses from the cavity region, related to the intrinsic Q -factor of each mode. (c) Broadband transmission spectrum of the bichromatic cavity normalized to the input power measured outside the chip, the three highlighted modes have been used to perform the SFWM experiment reported in the following. (d-i) Close-up of the three modes highlighted in panel: (d-f) normalized transmission (the red line is a fit with a Fano lineshape). (g-i) reflection spectra (the red line is a fit including a sinusoidal and a Fano-type contribution). From the visibility of the resonances in reflection, the coupling efficiency is estimated.

FIG. 2: Statistics of the spectral alignment for a cohort of 60 cavities. The red dashed line is a Gaussian fit of the histogram. It was possible to label the triplet composed by modes 1, 2 and 3 on 54 out of the 60 measured cavities. The second and third triplet were then found in 39 and 30 cavities, respectively. The average $\delta\Delta$ are $\overline{\delta\Delta}_{123} = -4.5$ GHz with a standard deviation $\sigma_{123} = 69.8$ GHz, $\overline{\delta\Delta}_{234} = 17.5$ GHz with $\sigma_{234} = 56.9$ GHz and $\overline{\delta\Delta}_{345} = 23.32$ GHz with $\sigma_{345} = 54.6$ GHz.

FIG. 3: Franson interferometry experimental setup. The input polarization is optimized with a fibered polarization controller (PC). A fiber Bragg grating is used to suppress the pump laser. At the output of the stabilized Franson interferometer the pairs are split and filtered, and the pump is further suppressed with free space filters. The polarization is again optimized before impinging on single-photon detectors. Time tags are collected and analyzed with an electronic correlator board.

FIG. 4: (a) Measured second-order cross-correlation function for signal and idler photon counts. A high coincidence-to-accidental ratio $CAR \approx 14$ is inferred from comparison between peak and background, suggesting a negligible contribution from higher-order pair emission. The estimated coupled pump power is -9 dBm. (b) Power-dependent scaling of the estimated internal generation rate. The orange line is a quadratic fit of the data. (c) Arrival time histogram at the output of the Franson interferometer, as a function of the time delay τ , where the time bins have been labelled with the corresponding ket states and of the interferometer phase ϕ . The three peaks as a function of delay are associated with the states $|SL\rangle$, $|LS\rangle$ and the state $|\psi\rangle$, the latter yielding quantum interference upon variation of the interferometer phase ϕ (see main text). (d) Franson interferogram associated with the central shown peak in panel c. The experimental data (blue dots) correspond to the integral of the central coincidence peak in panel c within a FWHM. A $85 \pm 2.5\%$ visibility is retrieved from sinusoidal fit (orange curve).